

Effective Entropy, Decoherence, Thermality, and Relational Time from Deterministic Dynamics under Restricted Access

(an explicit timeless-clock construction and a reduced-description synthesis)

Wynand Dednam^{1,*} and Leandro Boonzaaier²

¹ Research and Academic Computing: High-Performance Computing (HPC),
College of Science, Engineering and Technology,
University of South Africa, New Muckleneuk, Tshwane 0001, South Africa;
dednaw@unisa.ac.za

² rain Networks (Pty) Ltd, Cape Quarter, Green Point 8501, South Africa;
leandroboonzaaier90@gmail.com

* Correspondence: dednaw@unisa.ac.za

Abstract

We develop a conservative reduced-description framework in which effective mixedness, entropy increase, decoherence, and thermality arise not from stochastic microdynamics but from deterministic evolution (Hamiltonian or unitary) combined with restricted access to correlations. The central claim is structural: global dynamics can remain invertible while operationally relevant descriptions become non-invertible once an observer is limited to a subalgebra of observables and/or must trace over inaccessible degrees of freedom.

To make this mechanism explicit in a single, nontrivial example, we present a finite-dimensional Page–Wootters-style timeless-clock construction in which the global quantum description is stationary (constraint-based) and fully unitary, yet conditioning on a locally accessible clock subsystem induces an effective time ordering. Tracing over an inaccessible environment generates rapid entropy growth and long-lived saturation in the clock-conditioned reduced system state, accompanied by strong suppression of coherence. The construction provides an explicit benchmark for entanglement-driven equilibration and an emergent thermodynamic arrow within strictly orthodox quantum mechanics, without collapse postulates, stochastic noise models, or modifications of unitarity.

1 Introduction

Across classical nonlinear dynamics, quantum theory, and black-hole physics, one repeatedly encounters the same tension: microscopic laws can be deterministic (Hamiltonian flow or unitary evolution), yet the operationally relevant description available to an observer is often effectively mixed, entropy-producing, and approximately thermal. In this paper we adopt a deliberately conservative stance: we do *not* modify standard dynamics and we do *not* invoke fundamental stochasticity or wavefunction collapse. Instead, we treat effective mixedness and irreversibility as properties of *reduced descriptions* induced by restricted access to degrees of freedom and correlations, i.e. by restricting the accessible algebra of observables and/or tracing over inaccessible subsystems [1–3].

This “restricted-access” viewpoint is familiar in multiple guises. In classical chaos, deterministic stretching and folding transfers microscopic detail into fine-scale phase-space structure, so that any fixed finite resolution yields effective unpredictability and coarse-grained entropy growth. In quantum theory, entanglement with unobserved degrees of freedom yields mixed reduced states and suppresses interference between coarse alternatives (decoherence) while global evolution remains unitary [4–7]. In black-hole settings, causal structure enforces tracing over inaccessible regions, so exterior observables are described by mixed, approximately thermal reduced states [8, 9]. Recent relational approaches to time provide a further use case: globally stationary descriptions can yield an effective time parameter only after conditioning on a clock subsystem [10–13]. Separately, operational and thermodynamic analyses of quantum clocks quantify constraints on timekeeping and the cost of extracting classical records [14, 15].

While these themes are well developed individually, they are typically explored in isolation. Relational (Page–Wootters–type) constructions demonstrate how temporal ordering can emerge from a stationary global description [10, 12], but are usually formulated without an environment and therefore without entropy production or equilibration. Conversely, unitary equilibration and decoherence models demonstrate entropy saturation by tracing over inaccessible degrees of freedom, but presuppose an external time parameter and do not employ a timeless or constraint-based description. Recently, Shaari [13] presented an extended finite-dimensional Page–Wootters model in which tracing out inaccessible degrees of freedom induces entropy growth in clock-conditioned system states, thereby defining an informational arrow of time. The present work provides a complementary benchmark construction: rather than introducing explicitly parameterized unital noise channels (such as dephasing or depolarizing maps) whose entropy increase is monotonic, we use a deterministic entangling unitary with internal mixing dynamics and emphasize long-lived entropy saturation (effective equilibration) in the clock-conditioned reduced state under strict global unitarity and without clock-induced non-unitarity.

Contribution

The contribution is twofold. First, we formulate a compact interpretational template: *deterministic microdynamics + restricted access* \Rightarrow effective mixedness, entropy increase, and thermality in reduced descriptions. Second, we provide an explicit toy construction that realizes the template in one place: a Page–Wootters-style clock–system–environment model in which (i) the global description is stationary/unitary, (ii) an effective time ordering arises by conditioning on a clock, and (iii) entropy and coherence suppression emerge in the reduced system state purely from tracing over an inaccessible environment. This toy model is not used merely as “illustration”: it provides a concrete finite-dimensional benchmark demonstrating that effective irreversibility and temporal ordering can coexist with strict unitarity and global stationarity, complementary to recent PaW extensions that implement restricted access via explicit noise-channel constructions [13].

Operational anchors

Although the present manuscript is interpretational, the restricted-access mechanism it emphasizes is operationally realized in modern experiments. In macroscopic matter-wave interferometry, for example, observed fringe visibility is reduced not only by intended unitary evolution but also by unavoidable averaging over uncontrolled phases and by physical decoherence channels (e.g. background-gas scattering and thermal radiation) that entangle the probe with inaccessible degrees of freedom; see Ref. [16] for a recent large-nanoparticle demonstration and an explicit contrast model. Likewise, in autonomous and operational approaches to quantum clocks, the meaning of

time readout is tied to locally accessible records and thermodynamic constraints [14, 15].

Scope control

We do not derive the Born rule, the operator-algebraic origin of noncommutativity, or the numerical values of \hbar or c . We also do not propose new dynamics or claim a resolution of the single-outcome problem beyond standard decoherence-based accounts of emergent classicality. In contrast to relational-time approaches that attribute decoherence to intrinsic clock imperfections or effective non-unitary dynamics [11, 17], the present construction attributes entropy growth exclusively to restricted access to correlations with an inaccessible environment, while maintaining exact unitarity at the global level; see also the complementary “restricted access \Rightarrow informational arrow” perspective in PaW-type models developed by Shaari [13]. Our aim is interpretational and structural: to clarify what follows within orthodox physics once restricted access is treated as a first-class element of description.

Supplementary Material

To maintain focus on the central construction, auxiliary illustrative numerics and implementation details are collected in a Supplementary Material document. The present manuscript is self-contained with respect to the conceptual and mathematical development.

2 Restricted access as the source of effective mixedness

The core idea can be stated without commitment to any particular interpretation of the quantum state. Let the global state (classical distribution or quantum density operator) evolve deterministically and invertibly. Operationally, however, an observer accesses only a restricted algebra of observables and/or only a subsystem. This induces a reduced description: coarse graining in classical phase space, or partial tracing/restriction of states in quantum theory. The resulting mapping from global to operational descriptions is generically many-to-one and hence non-invertible, even when the underlying dynamics are invertible [1, 2].

For a quantum factorization $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_S \otimes \mathcal{H}_E$, restricted access to S yields

$$\rho_S(t) = \text{Tr}_E \rho(t), \tag{1}$$

so that $\rho_S(t)$ is generically mixed once entanglement with E develops. In this reduced-description viewpoint, “irreversibility” and “entropy increase” are statements about operational states and coarse-grained records, not about a breakdown of unitarity.

3 Central result: a timeless-clock construction with entropy saturation

Figure 1: Schematic overview of the timeless-clock construction and reduced-description mechanism. The global state $|\Psi\rangle$ is stationary and evolves unitarily on the full Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_C \otimes \mathcal{H}_S \otimes \mathcal{H}_E$. Operational time emerges only upon conditioning on a clock subsystem, while tracing over inaccessible environmental degrees of freedom yields an entropic, decohering reduced description $\rho_S(t)$. Entropy growth and the arrow of time arise at the level of the reduced description, not from any breakdown of unitarity.

3.1 History state and stationarity constraint

We consider a finite-dimensional clock C with basis $\{|t\rangle_C\}_{t=0}^{d-1}$, a system S , and an environment E ,

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_C \otimes \mathcal{H}_S \otimes \mathcal{H}_E. \quad (2)$$

A Page–Wootters-style “timeless” description may be expressed as a constraint

$$H_{\text{tot}}|\Psi\rangle = 0, \quad (3)$$

or, in discrete-time form, as an eigenvalue condition for a joint constraint unitary. A convenient explicit realization is the history state

$$|\Psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}} \sum_{t=0}^{d-1} |t\rangle_C \otimes |\psi_t\rangle_{SE}, \quad |\psi_t\rangle_{SE} = U^t |\psi_0\rangle_{SE}, \quad (4)$$

In the minimal construction considered here, the clock does not directly couple to the environment; entropy growth arises solely from system–environment entanglement under unitary evolution. This history state is stationary under the discrete constraint dynamics (equivalently, an eigenstate of the corresponding shift–evolution operator).

3.2 Emergent time by conditioning

Operational time enters only when an observer conditions on the clock reading, as in relational-time constructions [10]. Tracing out E gives

$$\rho_{CS} = \text{Tr}_E (|\Psi\rangle\langle\Psi|). \quad (5)$$

Let $\Pi_t := |t\rangle\langle t|_C$ denote the projector onto the clock reading t . The (unnormalized) state of S associated with the event “ $C = t$ ” is obtained by restricting ρ_{CS} to the corresponding clock sector and then discarding the clock degree of freedom,

$$\tilde{\rho}_S(t) = \text{Tr}_C [(\Pi_t \otimes I_S)\rho_{CS}]. \quad (6)$$

The probability of obtaining the clock outcome t is

$$p(t) = \text{Tr}[(\Pi_t \otimes I_S)\rho_{CS}] = \text{Tr} \tilde{\rho}_S(t), \quad (7)$$

so the normalized conditional state of S at clock time t is

$$\rho_S(t) = \frac{\tilde{\rho}_S(t)}{p(t)} = \frac{\text{Tr}_C [(|t\rangle\langle t|_C \otimes I_S)\rho_{CS}]}{\text{Tr} [(|t\rangle\langle t|_C \otimes I_S)\rho_{CS}]} \quad (8)$$

Thus, even if the global description is stationary/unitary, the reduced description yields an effective time-ordered family $\{\rho_S(t)\}$.

3.3 Restricted access and entropy saturation under strict unitarity

Because U generically entangles S with E , the reduced conditional state $\rho_S(t)$ is mixed for most t . We quantify effective mixedness by the von Neumann entropy

$$S(\rho_S(t)) = -\text{Tr}[\rho_S(t) \ln \rho_S(t)]. \quad (9)$$

In the numerical implementation used here (implementation details are provided separately), S is a qubit and E is a finite but larger multi-qubit environment with internal mixing dynamics. The resulting reduced description exhibits rapid entropy growth toward the maximal qubit value $\ln 2$ and remains close to that plateau over long clock times, while off-diagonal coherence is strongly suppressed (see Supplementary Material for the coherence diagnostic). For completeness, we also display the coherence proxy in Fig. 3, which is suppressed throughout the entropy plateau. The absence of fundamental irreversibility is not a limitation of the construction but an essential feature: it demonstrates that an entropic arrow and long-lived equilibration can arise in a reduced description even when the underlying dynamics remain strictly invertible.

Figure 2: Central toy-model result: entropy saturation under restricted access in a timeless-clock construction. We compute $\rho_S(t)$ via conditioning on a clock reading, Eq. (8), and tracing out an inaccessible environment. Despite strictly unitary global microdynamics (and a history-state realization of a timeless constraint), the reduced description exhibits rapid entropy increase and long-lived saturation near $\ln 2$, consistent with effective equilibration of a qubit entangled with a large inaccessible environment. Residual bounded fluctuations reflect finite-dimensional unitary dynamics rather than fundamental stochasticity.

Figure 3: Coherence proxy $|\rho_S(t)_{01}|$ (log scale) for the same toy-model parameters as Fig. 2. Off-diagonal elements in the computational basis are rapidly suppressed as entanglement with the environment develops, and remain small throughout the long-lived entropy plateau. Residual bounded fluctuations reflect finite-dimensional unitary dynamics rather than dissipative decay.

This single explicit construction captures the central interpretational point of the paper: global determinism and (constraint-)stationarity are compatible with effective temporal ordering and an emergent thermodynamic arrow once one restricts access to correlations and conditions on a local clock subsystem.

Figure 4: Purity $\text{Tr}(\rho_S(t)^2)$ under strictly unitary evolution. (a) With entangling interaction active, purity decreases toward $\approx 1/2$, indicating entanglement generation between S and E . (b) With the controlled-phase interaction switched off (all $\phi_k = 0$ so $U_{SE} = U_S \otimes U_E$), no entanglement is generated and purity remains identically 1. This confirms that reduced-state entropy increase and coherence suppression in the central toy model are entanglement-driven consequences of restricted access, not stochasticity or dissipation.

Figure 4 provides a basis-invariant mixedness diagnostic consistent with Fig. 2 and Fig. 3.

4 Limitations and failure modes

To avoid overclaiming, we emphasize the following limitations.

- **No fundamental irreversibility.** The construction remains fully unitary; long-time revivals are not forbidden in principle. The observed long-lived plateaus are effective and depend on environment size and mixing.
- **No Born rule derivation.** Conditioning on clock readings and reduced states is used operationally; no attempt is made to derive probability rules.
- **No unique pointer basis.** Decoherence-like behavior depends on the structure of system–environment coupling and the chosen coarse description.
- **Not a new theory of time.** The relational-time remark is included as a use case for restricted access, not as a claim to novelty in timeless formulations.

5 Conclusion

We have presented a reduced-description framework in which effective mixedness, entropy increase, thermality, and (in relational constructions) temporal ordering arise from deterministic microdynamics plus restricted access to correlations. The central result is an explicit timeless-clock toy model: a global stationary/unitary description yields an effective time-ordered reduced state by conditioning on a clock, while tracing over an inaccessible environment produces rapid entropy saturation and strong coherence suppression over long clock times. In this viewpoint, the emergence

of a thermodynamic arrow (entropy increase) and the emergence of a local temporal ordering are parallel consequences of restricted access to correlations under otherwise deterministic microdynamics [14, 18, 19].

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References

- [1] Rudolf Haag. *Local Quantum Physics: Fields, Particles, Algebras*. Springer, 1992.
- [2] Sebastien Fortin and Olimpia Lombardi. Partial traces in decoherence and in interpretation: What do reduced states refer to? *Foundations of Physics*, 44:426–446, 2014.
- [3] Guido Bacciagaluppi. The role of decoherence in quantum mechanics. Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, 2003. <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/qm-decoherence/>.
- [4] Wojciech H. Zurek. Decoherence, einselection, and the quantum origins of the classical. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 75:715–775, 2003.
- [5] Erich Joos, H. Dieter Zeh, Claus Kiefer, Domenico Giulini, and Joachim Kupsch. *Decoherence and the Appearance of a Classical World in Quantum Theory*. Springer, 2nd edition, 2003.
- [6] Maximilian Schlosshauer. Decoherence, the measurement problem, and interpretations of quantum mechanics. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 76:1267–1305, 2004.
- [7] H. Dieter Zeh. Roots and fruits of decoherence. In *Quantum Decoherence: Poincaré Seminar 2005*. Springer, 2007. Also available as arXiv:quant-ph/0512078.
- [8] Vijay Balasubramanian and Bartłomiej Czech. Quantitative approaches to information recovery from black holes. *Classical and Quantum Gravity*, 28:163001, 2011.
- [9] Alejandro Perez. Black hole entropy and Planckian discreteness. 2023. arXiv:2310.19389.
- [10] Don N. Page and William K. Wootters. Evolution without evolution: Dynamics described by stationary observables. *Physical Review D*, 27:2885–2892, 1983.
- [11] Rodolfo Gambini, Rafael A. Porto, Jorge Pullin, and Santiago Torterolo. Conditional probabilities with dirac observables and the problem of time in quantum gravity. *Physical Review D*, 79:041501, 2009.
- [12] Claudio Foti, Alessandro Coppo, Alessandro Cuccoli, and Paola Verrucchi. Time and classical equations of motion from quantum entanglement via the page and wootters mechanism. *Nature Communications*, 12:3567, 2021.
- [13] Jesni Shamsul Shaari. Informational arrow of time in an extended two-qubit page-wootters model. *Physics Letters A*, 577:131456, 2026.

- [14] Paul Erker, Mischa P. Woods, Ralph Silva, Nicolas Brunner, and Jonathan Oppenheim. Autonomous quantum clocks: Does thermodynamics limit our ability to measure time? *Phys. Rev. X*, 7:031022, 2017.
- [15] Vivek Wadhia, Florian Meier, Federico Fedele, Ralph Silva, Nuriya Nurgalieva, David L. Craig, Daniel Jirovec, Jaime Saez-Mollejo, Andrea Ballabio, Daniel Chrastina, Giovanni Isella, Marcus Huber, Mark T. Mitchison, Paul Erker, and Natalia Ares. Entropic costs of extracting classical ticks from a quantum clock. *Physical Review Letters*, 135:200407, 2025.
- [16] Sebastian Pedalino, Bruno E. Ramírez-Galindo, Richard Ferstl, Klaus Hornberger, Markus Arndt, and Stefan Gerlich. Probing quantum mechanics with nanoparticle matter-wave interferometry. *Nature*, 649:866–870, 2026.
- [17] Rodolfo Gambini, Rafael A. Porto, and Jorge Pullin. Realistic clocks, universal decoherence, and the black hole information paradox. *Physical Review Letters*, 93:240401, 2004.
- [18] Alessandro Coppo, Alessandro Cuccoli, and Paola Verrucchi. Magnetic clock for a harmonic oscillator. *Physical Review A*, 109:052212, 2024.
- [19] A. N. Pearson, Y. Guryanova, P. Erker, E. A. Laird, G. A. D. Briggs, M. Huber, and N. Ares. Measuring the thermodynamic cost of timekeeping. *Physical Review X*, 11:021029, 2021.